

Sustain Sahel

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I. Executive summary

Agroforestry plays a vital role in maintaining and developing the resilience and productivity of farms and landscapes. Scientific evidence from the Sahel region suggests that integration of trees and shrubs has the potential to improve temperature and moisture levels whilst providing bio-based fertiliser that contributes to increased yields of annual crops. However, little is known about the factors that influence the diffusion of agroforestry. This study examines joint decisions on the use of agroforestry alongside other complementary agricultural practices and disentangles agroforestry awareness from adoption choices and disadoption decisions. Our analysis is based on a comprehensive farm-level dataset covering almost 3,000 farm households in Mali and Senegal. A large number of adoption determinants are utilised, with a special focus on information access, information flows and social groups. The findings suggest that extension access and training participation boost awareness of agroforestry-based soil fertility management, while information provided by public extension, NGOs and community members are strongly associated with higher adoption intensity. In the analysis of disadoption, farmer-to-farmers exchange in the community was found to be a key factor in the persistence in agroforestry use. Membership in cooperatives and youth groups appear to have a favourable effect on awareness and adoption in Mali, but less so in the Senegalese case. Similarly, only results from Mali show that adoption of agroforestry is accompanied by the adoption of other sustainable intensification practices and a lower use in synthetic pesticides. We conclude that in order to support the transition to more widespread agroforestry-based soil fertility management, it is essential to strengthen public and NGO-based advisory systems that fully engage with local knowledge networks.

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2. Uptake of agroforestry-based crop management in the semi-arid Sahel - Analysis of joint decisions and adoption determinants

2.1 Introduction

Across the globe, food systems face the triple challenge of ensuring food and nutrition security for a growing population, providing livelihoods for farmers and others in the food chain, and improving environmental sustainability (Barrett et al., 2021). When it comes to crop production, sustainable intensification has been widely promoted in many low- and middle-income countries to reconcile economic and environmental objectives in agricultural development (Pretty et al., 2011; Kuyper and Struik, 2014; Rockström et al., 2017; Cassman and Grassini, 2020). Agroforestry, as one of the key sustainable intensification strategies, plays a vital role in enabling farms and landscapes to achieve greater resilience and productivity (Nair and Garrity, 2012; Mbow et al., 2014; Catacutan et al., 2018; Kay et al., 2019; Muchane et al., 2020). Policy-makers have put agroforestry firmly on the agenda for food system transformation and climate smart agriculture (FAO, 2013, 2016; HLPE, 2019). It is also key to redesigning production systems along agroecological principles (Pretty et al., 2011). As in other parts of the globe, agroforestry helps to provide benefits for the environment, farmer livelihoods and food sovereignty in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (Mbow et al., 2014; Bogie et al., 2018; Leroux et al., 2022).

The Sahel region is particularly vulnerable to climate and other shocks, where frequent droughts hamper efforts to eliminate malnutrition and alleviate rural poverty (Läderach et al., 2021). The integration of shrubs and trees into cropping systems is particularly promising in this context. Underlying factors for realising the benefits of agroforestry are hydraulic redistribution of water among the trees or shrubs and crops, availability of tree and shrub residues to improve soil health, and diversification of nutrition and income sources (Sinare and Gordon 2015). In Niger, long-term research has demonstrated the positive livelihood impacts of farmer managed natural regeneration of existing tree crops (Tougiani et al., 2008). Scientific evidence from Senegal suggests that the integration of trees and crops has great potential to positively affect ecosystem services, such as temperature and moisture levels, and to ultimately increase yields (Bayala et al., 2015; Bright et al., 2017; Bogie et al., 2018). Harnessing these factors is essential to help meet the future challenges in food security and sustainable development in the Sahel and elsewhere.

Despite these benefits and decades of promotion of agroforestry practices by national and international organizations, the adoption and practice of agroforestry remains not well documented and understood. Improving the effectiveness of agroforestry diffusion, requires a deeper understanding of the farmers' decision-making around agroforestry practices. A substantial literature exists on the determinants of adoption of agricultural practices, with a focus mostly on agronomic aspects and supporting interventions, such as improved varieties, new crop protection sprays or mineral fertiliser subsidies (e.g. Arslan et al., 2020; Pannell and Zilberman, 2020; Piñeiro et al., 2020; Ruzzante et al., 2021). Less is known about the factors that influence the diffusion and adoption dynamics of agroforestry or similar agroecological approaches (Arslan et al., 2020). Regression models may necessitate some simplification of farmers' binary adoption decision making on technological changes, however, context specific processes must also be accounted for (Glover et al., 2019). The concept of technology adoption (along with the related concepts of diffusion and scaling) is commonly used to design development interventions, to frame impact evaluations and to inform decision-making about new investments in development-oriented agricultural research. However, binary adoption simplifies what happens during processes of technological change. In all but the very simplest cases, it is likely to be inadequate to capture the complex reconfiguration of social

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and technical components of an innovation. While some simplification is needed in the quantitative estimation of adoption models, it is important to consider not only the binary adoption decision itself, but to understand the process and context of farm-level choices (Pannell and Zilbermann, 2020). Therefore, the present study aims i) to shed light on decisions to jointly adopt agroforestry alongside other agricultural practices and, ii) to disentangle awareness, adoption and disadoption. The analysis is based on the premise that agroforestry provides tangible socio-economic returns and, under the right circumstances, adoption is a rational choice.

For the purpose of our research, agroforestry is defined as the active management of shrubs and trees for improved soil fertility and crop productivity. These two aspects also emerged as the dominant agroforestry benefits perceived by farmers included in our survey. Therefore, when we refer to agroforestry, it involves assisted natural regeneration of shrubs and trees and the active utilisation of their residues as fertilizer. While there are multiple other benefits of agroforestry, for example the provision of nutrient-dense foods and livestock fodder, their exhaustive inclusion is beyond the scope of this study. Our analysis relies on a comprehensive farm-level dataset covering almost 3,000 farm households. As part of the SustainSahel project, the dataset was collected in 2019 in Mali and in 2020 in Senegal. From the data, response variables were specified regarding awareness, uptake and abandonment of agroforestry as well as of other agricultural practices. At the same time, a large number of adoption determinants and control variables were available. Based on the relevance of training, extension and knowledge in recent adoption reviews (Arslan et al., 2020; Piñeiro et al., 2020; Ruzzante et al., 2021), in our analysis we focus in particular on the influence of information access and information flows, alongside aspects of social networks and other characteristics of the farmer and farm.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: The next section presents the study area and the data. In section 3, methodological considerations and econometric specifications are explained in detail, while section 4 highlights the major findings on awareness, adoption and disadoption decisions. These findings take a focus on agroforestry, but also examine the interrelations between agroforestry adoption and other agricultural practices. The results are discussed in section 5, which also draws attention to the main conclusions from our research.

2.2 Data

Study area and data collection

This study is carried out in the context of the Horizon 2020 project, SustainSahel. The project aims to promote the synergistic use and protection of natural resources for rural livelihoods through analysing and developing systematic integration of crops, shrubs and livestock in the Sahel. For this purpose, it identified a number of research sites in Burkina Faso, Mali and Senegal, which are representative of key Sahelian agroecosystems. To accommodate large scale structured surveys, adoption research in SustainSahel focuses on five of these sites, namely Fatick in Senegal as well as Kayes, Koulikoro, Segou and Sikasso in Mali. These sites cover cropping as well as integrated crop-tree-shrub systems in the semi-arid zone of the Sahel with annual rainfall between 500 and 900 mm (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005), with the exception of Sikasso, which has slightly higher precipitation (see map in Figure 1). Among others, important trees and shrubs at the study sites include *Faidherbia albida*, *Vitellaria paradoxa*, *Parkia biglobosa*, *Guiera senegalensis*, and *Piliostigma reticulatum*. The sites correspond roughly to administrative units, covering one whole region in Senegal and large parts of four distinct regions in Mali. To account for the specific country contexts, we split the sampling, data collection and analysis by country. Results are representative of the five sites we included, and indicative of trends in the wider semi-arid Sahel of West Africa. However, they are not representative for the entire countries, neither for the entire Sahel region.

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The study area also does not cover all sites of the SustainSahel project. As large-scales surveys are expensive to conduct, it was decided to focus activities of WP3 on two countries, i.e. Senegal and Mali. Burkina Faso does not have any WP3 activities, but we believe that results are also relevant for Burkina Faso, just like Niger.

To select farm households for data collection in both countries, a two-stage cluster sampling procedure was applied. In the first stage, we randomly selected 80 villages from a list of feasible villages at each of the five sites. The inclusion of a village was contingent on having agriculture as the main source of livelihood (including cereal and legume production). Once villages were selected, between seven and ten households per village were randomly selected to participate in the survey, depending on the overall farm household population at each site. This resulted a dataset covering 2168 farm households across the Kayes, Koulikoro, Segou and Sikasso sites in Mali and 720 farm household across 80 villages in the Fatick site of Senegal.

Figure 1: Map of the study area

For the data collection, a structured questionnaire was designed, consisting of approximately 250 questions covering plot, household, and village level characteristics. The questionnaire was designed in French but administered in the local languages to the household head. All enumerators and supervisors were trained for approximately two days to ensure that they were sufficiently familiar with the questionnaire and process before the field survey. We conducted a pre-test of the survey instrument before the actual data collection process, whereby two villages in each country were selected for the pre-testing. The pre-test experience was used to modify the questionnaire to ensure that the questionnaire was well-structured, easily understood by the enumerators, and devoid of ambiguity regarding the definition of the questions. The pre-test was also useful in determining the average time it takes to complete one questionnaire, which was approximately two hours. Data collection was carried out between June and August (2019 in Mali and 2020 in Senegal).

Response Variables

To get a comprehensive idea of adoption drivers and consider the diffusion process, response variables for agroforestry include awareness (whether farmers have heard of the practice), adoption (whether farmers have adopted the practice), adoption intensity (proportion of farm area, where the practice is used) and disadoption (whether farmers have discontinued the use of the practice after initial adoption). The primary deciding factor for inclusion of practices, either complementary or competing with agroforestry, was related to the general level of awareness of that practice, with five percent sample awareness as minimum cut off for practice inclusion. Consequently, we included four agroecological practices (in addition to agroforestry) and three conventional practices (Table 1). The first group of practices include mulching and composting, intercropping, improved rotations and the use of animal manure. These practices are commonly referred to as ecological intensification or climate-smart agricultural strategies in the literature (Arslan et al., 2020; Pannell and Zilberman, 2020; Piñeiro et al., 2020; Ruzzante et al., 2021). The second group is comprised of improved crop varieties, mineral fertilizer and synthetic pesticides. For all practices, we constructed awareness and use (adoption) measures from our data. These were coded as binary variables, whereby 1 indicates that a farmer is using the practice and 0 would indicate the reverse. See Table 1 for summary statistics covering the average use of these different factors across practices.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the response variables included in the econometric models

Variable description	Variable name	Unit	Mali (4 sites)		Senegal (Fatick)	
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD
<i>Agroforestry</i>						
Prop. of farm area covered by agroforestry	prop_AGFOR	[0-1]	0.132	0.303	0.289	0.410
Awareness of agroforestry	aware_AGFOR	[1 = yes]	0.514	-	0.554	-
Use of agroforestry at time of survey	use_AGFOR	[1 = yes]	0.213	-	0.399	-
Disadoption of agroforestry	disadop_AGFOR	[1 = yes]	0.069	-	0.017	-
<i>Other practices</i>						
Use of mulch composting at time of survey	use_MULCH	[1 = yes]	0.039	-	0.319	-
Use of intercropping at time of survey	use_INTCRP	[1 = yes]	0.149	-	0.165	-
Use of improved rotations at time of survey	use_IMP_ROTATION	[1 = yes]	0.132	-	0.206	-
Use of manure at time of survey	use_MANURE	[1 = yes]	0.480	-	0.711	-
Use of improved varieties at time of survey	use_VARIETIES	[1 = yes]	0.056	-	0.095	-
Use of mineral fertiliser at time of survey	use_FERTILISER	[1 = yes]	0.591	-	0.614	-
Use of synthetic pesticides at time of survey	use_PESTICIDES	[1 = yes]	0.356	-	0.541	-
Number of Observations			2,070		695	

Adoption determinants

Farmers adoption decision of the different practices described above is often influenced by a host of socio-economic (e.g., education, access to and ownership to assets), market and institutional (e.g., access to extension and credit) and environmental factors (e.g., soil types, rainfall patterns). Ruzzante et al. (2021) identified farmer education, household size, land area, access to credit, land tenure, access to extension services, and organization membership to positively correlate with the adoption of many agricultural technologies in low- and middle-income countries. For agroforestry in Africa more specifically, the review of Arslan et al. (2020) highlighted information, tenure, social groups and distance to roads and markets as important adoption determinants. We made sure to cover these factors in our analysis, with particular focus on extension and information, which we considered as most crucial leverage points in the context of the SustainSahel project and in the current policy discourse. Peer learning and co-creation are integral parts of an agroecological transition and thus of special interest when analysing agroforestry adoption dynamics (FAO, 2013). As shown in Table 2, we categorised variables according to relevance and use in

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the regression models into information access, information flows and remaining farmer and household characteristics. To better specify the models and provide relevant insights to potential action points for policy makers, we decided to focus the analysis on information access (through extension, mobility, media or training) and on information flows (in terms of information on sustainable agricultural practices from public extension, NGOs, farmer organisations, the community or the media). The extensive list of remaining variables has been primarily implemented to control for other possible determinants from the existing adoption literature and to improve the accuracy and descriptive power of our models. We thus included further variables relating to the farmer and the farm household, such as for example education, financial conditions, market integration and shock perception. See Table 2 for variable descriptions and summary statistics. The location dummies are not shown in the table, but nine control districts (“cercles”) were included in the estimation of the Mali models (Banamba, Kadiolo, Sikasso, Bla, Segou, Baraouli, Yelimane, Nioro du Sahel, Diema), with Koulikoro district as the base. For estimating the models based on the data from Fatick in Senegal, two districts (“arrondissement”) were used as location dummies (Niakhar and Tattaguine), while Diakhao district served as base.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of adoption determinants included in the econometric models

ID	Variable description	Variable name	Unit	Mali (4 sites)		Senegal (Fatick)	
				Mean	SD	Mean	SD
<i>Information access</i>							
1	Access to extension	EXTEN_ACS	[I = yes]	0.729	-	0.433	-
2	Access to motor vehicle	MOTOR_ACS	[I = yes]	0.736	-	0.188	-
3	Access to TV or radio	MEDIA_ACS	[I = yes]	0.821	-	0.751	-
4	Training participation (last 5 years)	TRAINING	[I = yes]	0.135	-	0.179	-
<i>Information flows</i>							
5	Information received from publ. extension	GOV_EXT_INFO	[I = yes]	0.574	-	0.115	-
6	Information received from NGO extension	NGO_EXT_INFO	[I = yes]	0.393	-	0.164	-
7	Information received from farmer org.	FARM_ORG_INFO	[I = yes]	0.298	-	0.129	-
8	Information received from community	COMM_INFO	[I = yes]	0.409	-	0.817	-
9	Information received from TV or radio	MEDIA_INFO	[I = yes]	0.158	-	0.086	-
<i>Other farmer and household characteristics</i>							
10	Membership of farm cooperative	COOP_MEM	[I = yes]	0.429	-	0.935	-
11	Membership of female society	FEM_SOC_MEM	[I = yes]	0.177	-	0.141	-
12	Membership of youth society	YOUTH_SOC_MEM	[I = yes]	0.295	-	0.126	-
13	Credit access	CREDIT	[I = yes]	0.328	-	0.029	-
14	Age of household head	AGE	[Years]	55.985	14.477	56.075	13.080
15	Education of household head	EDUC_YRS	[Years]	2.307	4.073	3.020	4.037
16	Farm experience of household head	EXPER_YRS	[Years]	37.508	16.819	39.495	7.322
17	Length of household head residence	VILLAGE_YRS	[Years]	55.129	21.570	54.558	14.385
18	Household size	HH_SIZE	[#]	25.103	17.435	13.149	6.158
19	Female to male ratio (> 15 years old)	ADLT_FEM_MAL_RATIO	[Ratio]	1.186	0.890	1.104	0.677
20	Females with income	NUM_FEM_INC	[#]	0.840	1.777	0.224	0.552
21	Males with income	NUM_MALE_INC	[#]	2.331	2.312	1.023	1.055
22	Household member emigration	MIGRATION	[I = yes]	0.499	-	0.642	-
23	Income from agriculture	TOT_HH_INC_AG	[Thousand CFA]	304.703	430.139	768.483	646.450
24	Income from outside agriculture	TOT_HH_INC_OTH	[Thousand CFA]	120.890	201.941	743.217	952.029
25	Farm ownership	OWN_FARM	[I = yes]	0.896	-	-	-
26	Cultivated area	CULTIV_HA	[Ha]	6.879	5.756	4.129	2.281
27	Tropical livestock units (cow, sheep, goat)	BOVID_TLSU	[TLSU]	10.166	15.093	5.135	8.619
28	Tropical livestock units (horse, donkey)	EQUID_TLSU	[TLSU]	9.485	12.966	2.435	1.442

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29 Proportion of sorghum and or millet	PROP_MILLETS	[0-1]	0.601	0.418	0.566	0.164
30 Proportion of groundnut and or cowpea	PROP_PULSES	[0-1]	0.075	0.194	0.418	0.162
31 Market integration index	QUANT_MKT_INTG RT	[Index]	0.129	0.229	0.232	0.176
32 Distance to market	MN_DIST_MKT	[Km]	8.852	8.909	5.706	3.118
33 Draft animal ownership	DRAFT	[1 = yes]	0.681	-	0.916	-
34 Subsistence farm	CONSUM_ONLY	[1 = yes]	0.571	-	0.171	-
35 Drought exposure	DRT_EXP	[1 = yes]	0.536	-	0.292	-
36 Flood exposure	FLOOD_EXP	[1 = yes]	0.125	-	0.122	-
37 Variable rainfall exposure	VAR_RAIN_EXP	[1 = yes]	0.458	-	0.148	-
Number of Observations			2,070		695	

Prior to use in this study, the raw data on all these variables was assessed for outliers. Observations were classed as outliers if they were greater than the 99th percentile for that particular variable. These outliers were then removed and replaced with a missing value. Subsequent, if missing values made up approximately 1% of the total observations, the missing values were replaced through imputation using selected variables as references. Only households that contained a full complement of observations were kept for the analysis. This resulted in the number of observations being slightly reduced from 2138 to 2070 for the Malian and from 720 to 695 for the Senegalese datasets.

2.3 Methods

In this section, we present the main empirical estimation strategies that were employed to understand farmers' adoption processes in the selected case study regions in Mali and Senegal. Drawing on the vast literature on agricultural technology adoption (e.g. Kpadonou et al., 2017), we first investigated farmers' joint adoption decision of the eight different agricultural practices outlined in Table I. Consideration of joint adoption decisions is vital to identify combinations of practices that are appropriate to a farm's own context. It highlights which practices either substitute/compete with or complement agroforestry. Subsequently, drivers of agroforestry uptake were examined in more detail. We systematically identified factors influencing farmers' awareness and adoption.

Joint Practice Decision Model

Improved agricultural practices are seldom adopted in isolation since the complementarity between particular sets of practices makes adopting them together advantageous for farmers. For instance, farmers in the Sahel face multiple production risks, which often leads to joint adoption of bundles of risk-reducing agricultural practices (Feder et al., 1985). Farmers bundle selection can be considered an expected utility maximizing problem (Dorfman, 1996), in that certain interrelations or differences between practices influence farmers' observed adoption decisions. For instance, some practices may be viewed as complements, while other are regarded as substitutes for each other. In our case, a farmer may for instance be more or less likely to uptake agroforestry if they already use a different practice. The use of shrubs and trees for soil fertility management is perhaps less prevalent if mineral fertilisers are used, while agroforestry use is possibly combined with the application of accumulated arboreal mulch to cultivated land. Moreover, the different practices reported in Table I are promoted to farmers frequently in combinations by governments and other stakeholders. In this regard, understanding the complex interrelated behavioural patterns underlying farmers adoption decision of these practices is expected to inform policies aimed at improving farmers resilience to climate related shocks.

We employed a Multivariate probit (MVP) model to account for the interdependent nature of farmers' adoption decision of the eight different practices outlined in Table I. That is, since farmers may choose

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to adopt a combination of practices jointly, failure to account for such interrelationships in the analysis of decision-making behaviour could lead to biased estimates and wrong policy conclusions (Greene, 2008). Within an MVP framework, we assume farmers to be rational decision makers and hence they are expected to choose a combination of agricultural practices that maximises their expected profits, in the sense that they will only adopt practices either individually or jointly if the net benefit from adoption is positive (Kpadonou et al., 2017). Thus, we consider farmers joint adoption decision of the following vector (P) of agricultural practices: agroforestry (A); mulching (M), intercropping (I), crop rotation (R), manure (N), improved crop varieties (C), mineral fertilizer (F) and synthetic pesticides (S) within an MVP framework. Let a farmer i 's latent (unobserved) net benefit from adoption of any given agricultural practice p (where $p \in P$) be denoted by (Y_{ip}^*) . The estimated model implies that a particular farm household would consider adopting a given practice if the net benefit from adoption is positive. Hence, we relate farmers observed adoption decision with their latent net benefit in the following manner:

$$y_{ip} = \beta_p X_i + \tau_i + \epsilon_{ip}; \quad y_{ip} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } Y_{ip}^* > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } Y_{ip}^* \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where y_{ip} is farmers observed adoption decision of agricultural practice (p); τ_i indicates district level control variables, which accounts for regional variations in terms of infrastructure, institutional support and agroecology. We also control for a vector of household and plot level exogenous factors (X_i) concerning access to information and information flows, just like farmer and household characteristics that affect farmers' adoption decision (see variables 1 to 37 reported in Table 2). Finally, the error term (ϵ_{ip}) is assumed to be identically and independently distributed across farmers but not across the adoption equations of a given farmer (Teklewold et al., 2013; Kpadonou et al., 2017b). That is, the error term (ϵ_{ip}) of the adoption equations which represents unobserved characteristics that affect farmers choice of the different practices is assumed to have a multivariate normal distribution with the following covariance matrix (Ω) structure

$$\Omega = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_{AM} & \rho_{AI} & \rho_{AR} & \rho_{AN} & \rho_{AC} & \rho_{AF} & \rho_{AS} \\ \rho_{MA} & 1 & \rho_{MI} & \rho_{MR} & \rho_{MN} & \rho_{MC} & \rho_{MF} & \rho_{MS} \\ \rho_{IA} & \rho_{IM} & 1 & \rho_{IR} & \rho_{IN} & \rho_{IC} & \rho_{IF} & \rho_{IS} \\ \rho_{RA} & \rho_{RM} & \rho_{RI} & 1 & \rho_{RN} & \rho_{RC} & \rho_{RF} & \rho_{RS} \\ \rho_{NA} & \rho_{NM} & \rho_{NI} & \rho_{NR} & 1 & \rho_{NC} & \rho_{NF} & \rho_{NS} \\ \rho_{CA} & \rho_{CM} & \rho_{CI} & \rho_{CR} & \rho_{CN} & 1 & \rho_{CF} & \rho_{CS} \\ \rho_{FA} & \rho_{FM} & \rho_{FI} & \rho_{FR} & \rho_{FN} & \rho_{FC} & 1 & \rho_{FS} \\ \rho_{SA} & \rho_{SM} & \rho_{SI} & \rho_{SR} & \rho_{SN} & \rho_{SC} & \rho_{SF} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The diagonal elements in the above matrix are normalised to 1 (for identification purposes), which allows the off-diagonal elements of the covariance matrix to be interpreted as the correlation between the stochastic components of the different practices. In particular, a positive (negative) and statistically significant coefficient in the off-diagonal covariance matrix suggests complementarity (substitutability) of the different agricultural practices.

Agroforestry adoption models

While the MVP framework described above considers farmers' joint adoption decision of agroforestry and the different practices outlined in Table 1 at the extensive margin (i.e., whether farmers have adopted the practices or not), it doesn't consider adoption at the intensive margin (i.e., proportion of farmland under agroforestry). From a policy perspective, it is key to identify the major factors that lead to greater intensity of adoption. Therefore, in a next step, we examined drivers of agroforestry uptake at the intensive margin. However, our data shows that only about 50% of the farmers were aware of agroforestry, suggesting the presence of sample selection related to differences in exposure and awareness

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about the active use of agroforestry-based soil fertility management. As such, non-adoption may either reflect the fact that farmers were unaware of the practice and hence were unable to decide on its uptake, or they were aware and decided to not adopt. This is important since farmers' adoption decision of agroforestry may involve a sequence of steps and endogenous choices. In our setup, this involves learning about the agroforestry and then deciding about use of agroforestry together with the allocation of farmland for agroforestry. Therefore, to capture the sequential nature of farmers adoption decision of agroforestry practices, we employed a two-step sample-selection model.

Our two-stage estimation strategy permits agroforestry exposure vs. non-exposure to be generated by different selection processes. More specifically, the selection variable in the first stage captures whether farmers have heard of agroforestry or not, whereas the response variable in the second stage captures the extent to which farmers have actively implemented agroforestry for soil fertility and crop productivity management. Empirically, our estimation strategy involves modeling farmers' awareness of agroforestry via a probit model and then estimating parameters of the adoption intensity via a generalized linear model (GLM). As our response variable is defined as adoption proportion which is bounded between zero and unity, a generalized linear model (GLM) with a binomial family for the error distribution and a logit link, based on (Papke and Wooldridge, 1996), was deemed to be more suitable compared to the standard Heckman model. A GLM model with sample selection bias has been implemented by (Miranda and Rabe-Hesketh, 2006) in Stata through the *ssm* routine. This allows for consistent estimation of a joint model of the response and selection variables through maximum likelihood estimation. The second stage GLM equation is specified as

$$y_i = \beta \hat{T}_i + \theta X_i + \delta V_i + \tau_i + \epsilon_{1i} \quad (3)$$

where y_i is the observed adoption extent by farmer i , \hat{T}_i is the first stage predicted probability of agroforestry awareness (see Eq. 4 below), τ_i indicates district level control variables and ϵ_{1i} is the error term of the adoption equation. Z_i captures farmer and household characteristics, but not information (see variables 10 to 37 in Table 2), while V_i defines adoption-relevant information flows via different channels (see variables 5 to 9 in Table 2). The decision of implementing agroforestry across the farm however hinges on a first stage selection equation expressed as

$$T_i = \phi Z_i + \gamma W_i + \tau_i + \epsilon_{2i} \quad (4)$$

Where T_i is a binary awareness variable (yes/no) for farmer i , τ_i indicates district level control variables and ϵ_{2i} is the error term of the selection equation. Z_i corresponds to the vector of characteristics in equation 3 (see variables 10 to 37 in Table 2), while W_i defines awareness-relevant information access variables (see variables 1 to 4 in Table 2). These variables include access to extension, ownership of a motorbike, ownership of TV or/and radio through which agroforestry information can be acquired and finally whether farmers have attended any form of training in the last 5 years. Based on the result from the MVP models and logic of innovation diffusion, we postulate that these variables are predominantly drivers of awareness. With correlation between ϵ_{1i} and ϵ_{2i} , a single stage GLM regression based on equation (3) would yield biased results. In this case the GLM model with sample selection provides consistent estimates for all parameters.

Disadoption model

A simple probit model was used to model disadoption of agroforestry. The sample was restricted to only include farms who had ever used agroforestry, so for the four sites in Mali this meant a sample of 584 observations and correspondingly a sample of 298 observations for Fatick in Senegal. However, when the

disadoption equation was calculated for Fatick there proved to be too few disadopters (13 out of the full sample of 695). This resulted in non-convergence of the probit model and therefore we omitted the disadoption results for Fatick.

2.4 Results

In this section, we report our main estimation results in four sub-sections. The first sub-section presents estimation results for the joint adoption specification described in Section 3.1 above. In the next two-subsection, we reported the agroforestry awareness and adoption estimation results across Mali and Senegal sites. The final sub-section presents estimates on the determinants of agroforestry disadoption in Mali.

Joint Adoption Decisions

MVP models for both country samples returned significant Wald tests, indicating that the models provide a good fit to the data. This is shown by the highly significant χ^2 tests statistics of 11,299 and 5,279 for Mali and Senegal respectively, both with $p > \chi^2 = 0.000$ (see Tables A1 and A2 in the appendix). The null hypothesis that all predicted regression coefficients are jointly equal to zero is strongly rejected in both models. From the significant coefficients in Table 3, it becomes apparent that the MVP model for the four sites in Mali provides evidence that decisions on agricultural practices comply with the joint decision framework. Our results provide an indication that the adoption choice of a certain practice is likely to be related to the choices made regarding the adoption of other practices. Results reported in Table 3 show that agroforestry adoption is complementary to the adoption of mulch composting, intercropping, improved rotation, manure application and the use of improved varieties. That is, farmers who utilise agroforestry are more likely to use one or more of these practices. On the other hand, the coefficient for agroforestry and the use of pesticides indicates that the active use of trees and shrubs is associated with a lower likelihood of using pesticides. Moreover, for the Mali sites, we find that adopting intercropping and the use of manure or improved varieties seem to be significantly positively correlated. Conversely, the use of mineral fertiliser and intercropping returns a significant negative correlation. Lastly the use of either pesticides or mineral fertiliser are seen to mutually reinforce the likelihood of adoption of one another.

Table 3. Correlation matrix of the multivariate probit model for joint decisions on practice adoption in the four Mali sites

Practice	AGFOR R	MULC H	INTRCR P	ROTATIO N	MANUR E	VARIETIE S	FERTILISE R	SPRAY S
AGFOR	1	0.131**	0.122**	0.140***	0.189***	0.289***	-0.037	-0.099**
MULCH	-	1	0.125*	-0.016	0.081	0.115	0.103	0.113**
INTRCRP	-	-	1	0.089	0.240***	0.215***	-0.183***	0.077
IMP_ROTATIO N	-	-	-	1	0.202***	0.127*	0.050	-0.003
MANURE	-	-	-	-	1	0.117*	-0.037	0.040
VARIETIES	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.004	-0.035
FERTILISER	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.232***
PESTICIDES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1

Likelihood Ratio Test $\rho = 0$ 139.6***

Note: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Evidence for joint decision-making was also found for the Fatick site in Senegal, with some noticeable differences between the results in Mali and Senegal. As shown in Table 4, we found no relationship between the decision to adopt agroforestry and any of the other practices apart from intercropping. However, some similarities can be found, with the decisions to use mulch composting and intercropping

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appearing to be correlated in both samples. Moreover, as was seen for the sites in Mali, the decision to implement the use of mineral fertilisers and synthetic pesticides could be regarded as complementary. Interestingly, in the Senegalese case, the decision for adoption of mulch composting appears to rather substitute for the use of manure, mineral fertiliser or synthetic pesticides.

Table 4. Correlation matrix of the multivariate probit model for joint decisions on practice adoption at the Fatick site, Senegal

Practice	AGFO R	MULC H	INTRCR P	ROTATIO N	MANUR E	VARIETIE S	FERTILISE R	SPRAY S
AGFOR	1	0.115	-0.132*	-0.093	0.038	0.131	-0.047	0.029
MULCH	-	1	0.337***	0.118	-0.161**	0.155*	-0.177***	0.184***
INTRCRP	-	-	1	0.563***	-0.406***	0.197*	0.065	-0.044
IMP_ROTATIO N	-	-	-	1	-0.022	0.125	0.006	-0.089
MANURE	-	-	-	-	1	0.068	-0.024	-0.135*
VARIETIES	-	-	-	-	-	1	-0.073	-0.145*
FERTILISER	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.126*
PESTICIDES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1

Likelihood Ratio Test $\rho = 0$ 113.7***

Note: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

In general, access to extension agents, ownership of motorised transport, ownership of a TV or radio and receipt of training in the preceding five years had no important associations with use of any of the eight practices. These four variables were subsequently used as instruments for awareness in the sample selection models. Receiving information on sustainable agricultural practices from community exchange was consistently seen to have significant positive associations with the use decision of all agroecological practices for both countries. Information from government or NGO extension services was also consistently associated with a greater likelihood of practice adoption. For further insights consult the appendix. It should be noted that MVP models made no sample selection correction as the estimations focus only on joint decisions.

Agroforestry awareness and adoption extent across the Mali sites

All three models used to understand awareness of agroforestry (probit) and the extent of agroforestry adoption (glm and ssm) are based on the full sample of 2,070 farmers and had significant Wald tests, which indicates that the models provide a good fit to the data. The tests had highly significant χ^2 test statistics of 330.6, 409.4 and 567.6 respectively, with $p > \chi^2 = 0.000$ for all three models. In addition, the SSM model produced a highly significant Likelihood Ratio Test giving a χ^2 statistic of 530.15 with a corresponding $p > \chi^2 = 0.000$ (see Table 5). This provides strong evidence of issues relating to sample selection. Therefore, the coefficient estimates in the uncorrected GLM model for the extent of use of agroforestry (Model 2, Table 5) can be considered biased. The SSM model (Model 3, Table 5) is a more appropriate model as the sample selection bias is factored into the estimation. Subsequently described results are thus those of Model 3.

The magnitude of coefficients, signs and significance levels for the determinant variables in both the awareness probit model (Model 1, Table 5) and the selection equation of the SSM model (Model 3, Table 5) were found to very be similar. The estimates however show some minor differences, which is due to the fact that, in Model 3, both the selection and outcome equation are estimated using the full maximum likelihood method. The only difference observed between Model 1 and the Model 3 selection equation was for the distance to market, with a greater distance being slightly positively significant in Model 1 (p -value = 0.088 in Model 1 versus 0.102 in the selection equation of Model 3). Access to extension services is positive and highly significant across both awareness estimations. Farm cooperative membership and

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credit are also significantly correlated with awareness of agroforestry (p -value = 0.000). Having a household member taking part in a youth association was also associated with a greater likelihood of awareness in both models (p -value = 0.006 respectively). Growing millet over a greater proportion of farmland and having higher off-farm income was related to a greater likelihood of awareness (p -values = 0.051 and 0.013 respectively). Conversely, a higher number of females who have a regular income and a larger household size was found to be associated with a lower likelihood of awareness (p -values = 0.002 and 0.057 respectively). Furthermore, if a farm is a subsistence farm, the model indicated a lower likelihood of agroforestry awareness (p -value = 0.002).

When the adoption intensity equations in Model 2 and Model 3 are compared, we see some large differences in the magnitude of the coefficients. This is due to the fact that the SSM model takes the sample selection bias into account. For instance, obtaining information on sustainable practices from government extension, NGO extension and community exchange are highly significant in both models but the magnitude of coefficients are approximately half to one third in the SSM model. Accessing sustainability information through the media is found to be significantly negatively related to adoption extent only in the SSM model (p -value = 0.015). Being a member of a farmer cooperative or having a youth association member in the household are found to be also highly positively related to adoption extent. However, having a household member who is a member of a female organisation was seen to be negatively associated with adoption extent (p -value = 0.013). Furthermore, having household members migrate, having experienced drought on the farm and having a larger cultivated area were all found to be significantly negatively related to agroforestry adoption extent (p -values = 0.002, 0.000 and 0.000 respectively). However, devoting a greater proportion of the farm to the production of millets or to pulses was highly significantly related to adoption extent (p -values = 0.000 for both). Having access to credit, a greater number of years of education, a larger number of male income earners and having ownership of the farm were all found to have a positive and significant relationship with agroforestry adoption below the 5% significance level.

Table 5. Maximum likelihood estimates of models explaining agroforestry awareness and adoption across the four Mali sites, with and without sample selection

Determinants	Model 1: Probit Model		Model 2: Simple GLM Model		Model 3: SSM Model (GLM + sample selection)			
	Awareness of Agroforestry (Y/N)		Extent of Agroforestry Use (%)		Selection Equation: Awareness (Y/N)		Adoption Equation: Extent of Use (%)	
	Coefficient	Robust SE	Coefficient	Robust SE	Coefficient	Robust SE	Coefficient	Robust SE
EXTEN_ACS	0.524***	0.071	-	-	0.512***	0.068	-	-
MOTOR_ACS	0.082	0.077	-	-	0.057	0.074	-	-
MEDIA_ACS	0.128	0.083	-	-	0.123	0.080	-	-
TRAINING	0.128	0.094	-	-	0.109	0.090	-	-
GOV_EXT_INFO	-	-	0.924***	0.151	-	-	0.362***	0.081
NGO_EXT_INFO	-	-	0.678***	0.141	-	-	0.289***	0.075
FARM_ORG_INFO	-	-	0.162	0.147	-	-	-0.024	0.076
COMM_INFO	-	-	1.121***	0.148	-	-	0.481***	0.080
MEDIA_INFO	-	-	-0.181	0.195	-	-	-0.250**	0.102
COOP_MEM	0.266***	0.065	0.628***	0.144	0.269***	0.065	0.364***	0.081
FEM_SOC_MEM	-0.061	0.087	-0.493**	0.202	-0.062	0.087	-0.278**	0.112
YOUTH_SOC_MEM	0.198***	0.073	0.350**	0.153	0.202***	0.073	0.226***	0.085
CREDIT	0.442***	0.077	0.274*	0.159	0.445***	0.077	0.192**	0.089
BANK	-0.176*	0.102	-0.016	0.211	-0.172*	0.101	0.020	0.115
AGE	0.005*	0.003	-0.002	0.006	0.005*	0.003	-0.001	0.003
EDUC_YRS	0.008	0.007	0.026*	0.015	0.009	0.007	0.017**	0.008
EXPER_YRS	-0.002	0.002	-0.003	0.005	-0.002	0.002	-0.002	0.003
VILLAGE_YRS	-0.002	0.002	0.005	0.004	-0.002	0.002	0.003	0.002

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HH_SIZE	-0.004**	0.002	-0.004	0.005	-0.004*	0.002	-0.002	0.003
ADLT_FEM_MAL_RAT	0.033	0.034	-0.073	0.084	0.031	0.034	-0.039	0.046
NUM_FEM_INC	-0.057***	0.019	-0.049	0.051	-0.060***	0.020	-0.029	0.027
NUM_MALE_INC	0.027*	0.016	0.093**	0.037	0.026*	0.016	0.047**	0.020
MIGRATION	0.068	0.063	-0.441***	0.138	0.071	0.064	-0.238***	0.077
TOT_HH_INC_AG	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000
TOT_HH_INC_OTH	0.000**	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000**	0.000	0.000	0.000
OWN_FARM	-0.062	0.104	0.560**	0.239	-0.052	0.103	0.314**	0.127
CULTIV_HA	-0.002	0.006	-0.084***	0.016	-0.002	0.006	-0.046***	0.009
BOVID_TLSU	0.004*	0.002	0.018***	0.004	0.005*	0.002	0.010***	0.002
EQUID_TLSU	-0.003	0.003	-0.004	0.006	-0.003	0.003	-0.002	0.003
PROP_MILLET	0.215**	0.107	1.270***	0.314	0.210*	0.107	0.700***	0.169
PROP_PULSES	0.028	0.172	2.314***	0.387	0.008	0.170	1.340***	0.211
DRAFT	-0.096	0.070	-0.336**	0.168	-0.090	0.070	-0.156*	0.092
CONSUM_ONLY	-0.243***	0.081	0.171	0.171	-0.246***	0.080	0.044	0.094
QUANT_MKT_INTGRT	-0.128	0.150	-0.380	0.377	-0.133	0.151	-0.193	0.210
MN_DIST_MKT	0.005*	0.003	-0.004	0.006	0.005	0.003	-0.002	0.003
DRT_EXP	0.126*	0.071	-0.907***	0.156	0.125*	0.071	-0.463***	0.088
FLOOD_EXP	-0.133	0.098	-0.187	0.223	-0.128	0.098	-0.089	0.119
VAR_RAIN_EXP	0.087	0.070	-0.119	0.152	0.090	0.070	-0.019	0.084
Constant	-1.057***	0.225	-4.534***	0.529	-1.037***	0.225	-2.392***	0.304
Observations	2,070		2,070		2,070			
χ^2 Statistic	330.6***		409.4***		567.6***			
Log Likelihood	-1,245		-583.2		-1,828			
Likelihood Ratio Test $p = 0$	-		-		530.15***			

Note: Location dummies are omitted; * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

These models were tested with and without the inclusion of data from the region of Sikasso. This was due to the difference in climate and ecosystem compared with the other regions. The results were robust for the two different samples, with only the results for credit access and farm ownership changing, becoming insignificant for adoption extent. In the full SSM presented in Table 5, both districts (Kadiolo and Sikasso) from the Sikasso site are included within the list of location control variables. These variables are expected to capture some of the geographic and climactic differences so analysis of all 4 Malian regions together should not be drastically affected by uncaptured local differences.

Agroforestry awareness and adoption extent in Fatick, Senegal

When modelling awareness and extent of agroforestry adoption in Senegal, there was a great degree of similarity with the results obtained for Mali, but also some clear differences. All three Senegalese models had significant Wald tests, which again show that these models fit the data well. All of the models had highly significant χ^2 tests statistics (116.1, 253.0 and 291.8 for Models 4, 5 and 6 respectively) and all χ^2 tests statistics were accompanied by a $p > \chi^2 = 0.000$ (see Table 6). The SSM model for Senegal returned a significant Likelihood Ratio Test with a χ^2 statistic of 38.55 and $p > \chi^2 = 0.000$. This indicates that we see a strong likelihood that the share of sample adopting agroforestry is affected by exposure bias in Senegal and consequently the SSM model, with its corrected coefficients (Model 6, Table 6), again provides a more correct interpretation of adoption drivers. The SSM model is thus the focus of the following paragraphs. In terms of the probit and selection equation for awareness of agroforestry (Model 4 and 6, Table 6), again both are very similar with only some minor differences associated with the different estimation techniques, discussed in the previous section. There are also relatively fewer significant coefficients for the Senegalese model compared to that of Mali, which in part is due to the fact the sample size is more limited. Extension access in Senegal appears to be marginally significant and positive for awareness, whilst having attended

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training in the last 5 years is highly significant and positively associated with awareness of agroforestry. We find also that having attained a higher level of education and also owning a greater amount of farm land is positively associated with awareness (p-values = 0.014 and 0.004 respectively). Moreover, ownership of draft animals for cultivation is seen to relate positively to awareness whilst a greater degree of market orientation was found to be negatively associated with agroforestry awareness (p-values = 0.000 and 0.043 respectively). Youth society membership, a greater number of years living in the same village, family migration, a greater distance from the local market and experience of drought were all minorly positively associated with agroforestry awareness in Senegal.

The differences between the GLM and SSM for extent of agroforestry adoption are more obvious, comparing Model 5 and Model 6 in Table 6, with the magnitude of coefficients tending to be approximately half once sample selection is corrected for. As was seen in Mali, gaining information on sustainable practices from government extension, NGO extension and community exchange were found to have a highly positive and highly significant relationship with the extent of agroforestry adoption. Learning about sustainable agricultural practices using these sources is therefore linked with a greater area of adoption relative to farm size. Conversely, hearing about sustainable agricultural practices from media sources is found to correlate negatively with extent of agroforestry adoption (p-value = 0.011). Like in the awareness and selection equations of Model 4 and 6, ownership of draft animals is positively correlated and higher degrees of market orientation is negatively correlated with extent of agroforestry adoption (p-values = 0.000 and 0.013). Lastly, having a greater number of cattle, sheep or goats (BOVID_TLSU) was minorly significantly related to a lower degree of agroforestry adoption. District dummies not shown in Table 6 captured some of the effect of different geographies, climates and cultures that are not explicitly included in these models.

Table 6. Model estimates for agroforestry awareness and adoption in Fatick, Senegal, with and without sample selection

Determinants	Model 4: Probit Model Awareness of Agroforestry (Y/N)		Model 5: Simple GLM Model Extent of Agroforestry Use (%)		Model 6: SSM Model (GLM + sample selection) Selection Equation: Awareness (Y/N) Adoption Equation: Extent of Use (%)			
	Coeff.	Robust SE	Coeff.	Robust SE	Coeff.	Robust SE	Coeff.	Robust SE
EXTEN_ACS	0.224*	0.122	-	-	0.226**	0.113	-	-
MOTOR_ACS	0.289*	0.150	-	-	0.251*	0.143	-	-
MEDIA_ACS	-0.003	0.127	-	-	0.027	0.114	-	-
TRAINING	0.521**	0.158	-	-	0.488***	0.148	-	-
GOV_EXT_INFO	-	-	1.521***	0.284	-	-	0.759***	0.154
NGO_EXT_INFO	-	-	1.451***	0.231	-	-	0.692***	0.122
FARM_ORG_INFO	-	-	0.414	0.617	-	-	0.074	0.330
COMM_INFO	-	-	0.847***	0.275	-	-	0.397***	0.137
MEDIA_INFO	-	-	-2.477**	1.228	-	-	-1.472**	0.576
COOP_MEM	0.243	0.183	-0.316	0.338	0.243	0.181	-0.149	0.189
FEM_SOC_MEM	-0.032	0.160	-0.232	0.257	-0.022	0.161	-0.137	0.143
YOUTH_SOC_MEM	0.296*	0.159	0.269	0.253	0.291*	0.159	0.135	0.144
CREDIT	-0.359	0.459	0.504	0.541	-0.326	0.462	0.309	0.296
BANK	0.202	0.299	-0.581	0.377	0.213	0.300	-0.311	0.209
AGE	-0.009	0.009	-0.001	0.014	-0.009	0.009	-0.001	0.008
EDUC_YRS	0.038**	0.015	0.023	0.023	0.038**	0.015	0.016	0.013
EXPER_YRS	0.000	0.004	0.005	0.006	0.000	0.004	0.002	0.004
VILLAGE_YRS	0.016*	0.008	0.010	0.012	0.016*	0.008	0.006	0.007
HH_SIZE	-0.009	0.010	-0.012	0.016	-0.010	0.010	-0.010	0.009

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ADLT_FEM_MAL_RAT	0.021	0.084	0.036	0.131	0.024	0.084	0.031	0.075	
NUM_FEM_INC	-0.009	0.107	-0.105	0.183	-0.005	0.106	-0.039	0.102	
NUM_MALE_INC	0.058	0.055	-0.175*	0.091	0.065	0.056	-0.081	0.052	
MIGRATION	0.232*	0.119	0.160	0.203	0.233*	0.120	0.096	0.115	
TOT_HH_INC_AG	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	
TOT_HH_INC_OTH	-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
CULTIV_HA	0.091**	*	0.032	0.002	0.060	0.093***	0.032	0.004	0.033
BOVID_TLSU	-0.002	0.008	-0.025*	0.014	-0.002	0.008	-0.014*	0.007	
EQUID_TLSU	-0.017	0.044	0.025	0.074	-0.016	0.044	0.018	0.041	
PROP_MILLETS	-0.026	1.121	-1.452	1.715	-0.088	1.136	-0.828	0.994	
PROP_PULSES	0.522	1.109	-0.447	1.658	0.475	1.121	-0.186	0.968	
DRAFT	0.894**	*	0.226	1.161***	0.313	0.906***	0.231	0.715***	0.191
CONSUM_ONLY	-0.001	0.187	0.111	0.297	-0.003	0.188	0.064	0.168	
QUANT_MKT_INTGR	-0.893**	0.453	-1.624**	0.680	-0.928**	0.458	-0.951**	0.385	
MN_DIST_MKT	0.032*	0.017	0.033	0.031	0.029*	0.017	0.022	0.018	
DRT_EXP	0.191	0.122	0.251	0.216	0.205*	0.124	0.138	0.121	
FLOOD_EXP	-0.206	0.175	-0.390	0.292	-0.199	0.176	-0.224	0.169	
VAR_RAIN_EXP	-0.056	0.155	0.066	0.263	-0.063	0.155	0.030	0.149	
Constant	-1.158	1.166	-1.178	1.705	-1.105	1.183	-0.678	0.995	
Observations	695	695	695	695	695	695	695	695	
χ^2 Statistic	161.1**	253**	291.8***	291.8***	291.8***	291.8***	291.8***	291.8***	
Log Likelihood	-385.3	-271.9	-648.1	-648.1	-648.1	-648.1	-648.1	-648.1	
Likelihood Ratio Test $\rho = 0$	-	-	38.55***	38.55***	38.55***	38.55***	38.55***	38.55***	

Note: Location dummies are omitted; * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Agroforestry disadoption across the Mali sites

The last model examined the agroforestry disadoption decisions of farmers. This model was run on the reduced sample of 584 farmer who stated that they had ever used agroforestry. Nevertheless, the model had a significant Wald tests with a χ^2 test statistic of 113.8 which is supported by a $p > \chi^2 = 0.000$ (see Table 7). Firstly, having received sustainable practice information from community exchange predicted a significantly reduced likelihood of disadoption (p -value = 0.010). Additionally, farmers with more years of education were seen to be less likely to stop using agroforestry (p -value = 0.004). On the other hand, receiving sustainability information from a farm organisation or having a member of the house hold take part in a female association was found to be correlated with a significantly larger chance of disadoption being observed (p -values = 0.034 and 0.003). Furthermore, having a member of the family take part in a youth association, a higher number of females or males with a regular income, owning draft animals and having experienced flooding on the farm were all significantly related to a lower chance of disadoption. Conversely, a higher ratio of females to males in the household, having experienced migration and having experienced drought were all linked with a greater likelihood below the 10% significance level.

Table 7. Model estimates for disadoption across all four Mali sites

Variable	Model 7: Probit Model	
	Disadoption of Agroforestry (Y/N)	
	Coeff.	Robust SE
GOV_EXT_INFO	0.142	0.167
NGO_EXT_INFO	0.018	0.135
FARM_ORG_INFO	0.320**	0.151
COMM_INFO	-0.392***	0.151
MEDIA_INFO	0.120	0.169

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COOP_MEM	-0.203	0.143
FEM_SOC_MEM	0.531***	0.181
YOUTH_SOC_MEM	-0.282*	0.153
CREDIT	-0.052	0.166
BANK	-0.295	0.202
AGE	0.004	0.007
EDUC_YRS	-0.042***	0.015
EXPER_YRS	0.005	0.005
VILLAGE_YRS	-0.004	0.005
HH_SIZE	-0.005	0.006
ADLT_FEM_MAL_RAT	0.143*	0.081
NUM_FEM_INC	-0.084*	0.051
NUM_MALE_INC	-0.087**	0.040
MIGRATION	0.234*	0.139
TOT_HH_INC_AG	0.000	0.000
TOT_HH_INC_OTH	0.000	0.000
OWN_FARM	0.015	0.234
CULTIV_HA	0.013	0.013
BOVID_TLSU	-0.005	0.005
EQUID_TLSU	0.003	0.008
PROP_MILLETS	0.342	0.282
PROP_PULSES	0.575	0.379
DRAFT	-0.403**	0.158
CONSUM_ONLY	-0.070	0.178
QUANT_MKT_INTGRT	0.448	0.363
MN_DIST_MKT	-0.006	0.006
DRT_EXP	0.273*	0.158
FLOOD_EXP	-0.374*	0.217
VAR_RAIN_EXP	0.038	0.167
Constant	-0.008	0.535
Observations	584	
χ^2 Statistic	113.8***	
Log Likelihood	-243.6	

Note: Location dummies are omitted; * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

2.5 Discussion

In agricultural innovation research, the concept of adoption is sometimes deemed inappropriate for its lack of temporal and spatial complexity (Douthwaite et al., 2003; Glover et al., 2019), so qualitative approaches are often suggested as the preferable method of analysis. While these approaches are key to an in-depth understanding of innovation processes, it is more difficult to obtain representative results and detect relationships in multivariate data. Precision and nuance have been added to the study of adoption through techniques that concentrate on evaluating the intensity of adoption (Arslan et al., 2020). Moreover, technological change involving multiple components can be somewhat captured by econometric models that analyse joint adoption decisions (Kassie et al., 2015; Glover et al., 2019). The present study tried to address shortcomings in the quantitative analysis of the adoption of agricultural practices by incorporating two perspectives into one analytical framework: decision-making on the joint use of several agricultural practices as well as adoption dynamics covering awareness, intensity of use and abandonment of agroforestry. Thereby, we aim to understand interaction effects of agroforestry with other practices together with its diffusion. While our study goes well beyond a binary adoption decision, it cannot shed full light on the experimentation and reconfiguration processes that happen along the way. This would require more specific tracing of innovation trajectories (e.g. Schut et al., 2020) as well as collection of representative panel data sets, which, whilst outside the scope of the analysis, is a key area for future research on this topic.

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Whereas panel data could more completely uncover the dynamics of farmers' choices to adopt, adapt and possibly give up agroforestry-based soil fertility management, our study is based on cross-sectional data. The dataset nevertheless provides a comprehensive picture of the status-quo of the knowledge about and the use of shrubs and trees for improving soil fertility and crop productivity across different contexts in Senegal and Mali. Between 51 and 55 percent of farmers at the five sites have heard of the practice in Mali and Senegal respectively, but only 21 and 40 percent are actually using agroforestry as specified in this analysis. The higher adoption rate in Senegal may be a result of long-term efforts to disseminate agroforestry-based soil fertility management at the Fatick site. Disadoption rates are relatively low, ranging from seven to two percent of farmers in Mali and Senegal respectively. The analysis shows that extension access, together with training participation in the case of Fatick, enhance awareness of agroforestry. Information on sustainable agricultural practices provided by public extension services and private NGOs, alongside community information flows and membership in social networks, are key drivers of agroforestry use. For disadoption, which we could only analyse with the Mali data, information exchange on sustainable agricultural practices in the community appears an important lever to encourage continued use of the practice. Youth and cooperative membership appear to have a favourable relationship with agroforestry use, albeit not significant for Fatick, Senegal. The fact that we see a negative association between membership in women's' groups and the intensity of agroforestry adoption is likely linked to the fact that these groups have been more focused on issues outside of agriculture.

Overall, our results are in line with the recent literature on adoption, stressing the importance of advisory services and farmer networks for innovation diffusion (Arslan et al., 2020; Pannell and Zilberman, 2020; Piñeiro et al., 2020; Ruzzante et al., 2021). By distinguishing between access to information, different information flows and social groups, we can better understand the diverse drivers of awareness, adoption and disadoption. It becomes apparent that agroforestry promotion is a multi-factorial challenge. For both the Malian and Senegalese contexts, our findings imply that investments in public or NGO extension support the dissemination of agroforestry-based soil fertility management. External advice needs to be coupled with promoting farmer-to-farmer exchanges in the community as well as efforts to encourage and nurture agriculturally orientated group participation. It is well known that the scaling of agroecological approaches has been shown to rely on horizontal peer learning (Bharucha et al., 2020). In India, the Andhra Pradesh Natural Farming programme plans to roll out agroecology to 6 million farmers in the state through a combination of farmer-based extension, government and NGO support and women groups. Participatory extension programmes are widely used to promote agricultural innovations and found to be effective, if properly implemented (Knook et al., 2020).

Our results capturing information flows and social networks are similar in the models estimated for the four Mali sites and for Fatick, which underscores their general validity. Meta-analysis performed by Ruzzante et al. (2021) highlights extension advice and organised interests as crucial determinants for the uptake of natural resource management practices. Arslan et al. (2020) have shown in their review that these variables are often positive and significant in agroforestry adoption studies in the SSA context. They also found that land tenure and distance to markets are key drivers. Our results, just like those of Ruzzante et al. (2021), confirm the first, but not the latter. In fact, proximity to markets may increase farmers' use of external inputs and thus decrease agroforestry-based soil fertility management. This could also be linked with the fact that better market access may predispose a farm towards more commercially-oriented monocropping. Distance to markets is also difficult to influence for decision-makers, while access to credit along with extension is one of the most likely variables to be shaped by policy (Ruzzante et al., 2021). Implementing agroforestry measures on the farm often requires medium to long-term investment decisions. Tenure and credit are considered key for farmers to invest into agroforestry (Ali et al., 2011). In this regard, evidence from Mali suggests that improved credit access should be combined with fostering

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knowledge and learning if the agroecological practices are to be scaled. In the case of Senegal credit access is also a positive, but not significant, driver of adoption.

Not only a combination of adoption drivers, but also combined decision-making on adoption shape the diffusion of agroforestry in the Sahel. Kassie et al. (2015) found that farmers located in eastern and southern Africa often take joint decision on the adoption of a set of sustainable intensification practices. In the Mali model, we also ascertained that agroforestry adoption is accompanied by the uptake of other sustainable intensification practices, such as mulching, rotations, use of manure and improved varieties, but by a reduction in synthetic pesticides. No clear pattern on joint decisions emerges from the results from Fatick, Senegal. This might be due to the higher overall level of commercialisation there and potentially due to a more limited geographical scope. We conclude that agroforestry uptake is generally complementary or unrelated to the use of other practices, with some indications of substitution, in that farmers who use synthetic pesticides are less likely to make use of agroforestry and vice versa. The signs for agroforestry-based soil fertility management and the use of mineral fertilisers are also negative, albeit not significant.

To support the transition to more widespread agroforestry-based soil fertility management, it is essential to strengthen public and NGO-based advisory systems that fully engage with local knowledge networks. Furthermore, solutions for agroforestry microfinance are needed to back up knowledge gains with the financial means for implementation.

2.6 Conclusions

Agroforestry-based crop management is an important strategy for ecological intensification in the semi-arid Sahel and evidence is needed on dissemination strategies. To obtain insights on innovation drivers in agroforestry, awareness, adoption intensity, disadoption and joint decisions should be considered. Our study reveals drivers of

- 1) Awareness of agroforestry
 - a. Extension access,
 - b. Participation in training
- 2) Extent of agroforestry use
 - a. Exposure to information on sustainable agriculture from public extension services
 - b. Exposure to information on sustainable agriculture from private NGOs
 - c. Information exchange on sustainable agricultural practices in the community
 - d. Membership in social networks
- 3) Continued use of agroforestry
 - a. Information exchange on sustainable agricultural practices in the community

In terms of joint decisions, we conclude that agroforestry uptake is generally complementary or unrelated to the use of other practices, with some indications of substitution, in that farmers who use synthetic pesticides are less likely to make use of agroforestry and vice versa. To support the transition to more widespread agroforestry-based soil fertility management, it is essential to strengthen advisory systems that fully engage with local knowledge networks. For capacity development purposes, agroforestry can be packaged together with most other practices found in the study area.

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3. Dissemination activities related with the Deliverable

News article on the SustainSahel website in April 2022: https://www.sustainsahel.net/news-archive.html?tx_news_pi1%5Baction%5D=detail&tx_news_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=News&tx_news_pi1%5Bnews%5D=2268&cHash=b2aa59b77fb64e663486d36315968725

Webinar on adoption study results with all SustainSahel partners and external advisors on 20 May 2022: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6933391135914528768/>

Researcher Dr. Assane Beye from UCAD spent 4 weeks at FiBL in September 2022 (presentations on WP3 Senegal with Department of Food System Sciences and Department of International Cooperation: https://www.sustainsahel.net/news-archive.html?tx_news_pi1%5Baction%5D=detail&tx_news_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=News&tx_news_pi1%5Bnews%5D=2724&cHash=241efa2b98b7591c14d5b907f841b808

Presentation of a poster on the adoption study at Tropentag 2022, which was held in September 2022 in Prague: [Proceedings forthcoming](#)

Adoption study scientific article submitted in October 2022 to *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*: [Review ongoing](#)